

Technical report

Validating User Journey Extension for Archimate (UJEA)

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This report serves to provide additional information to the paper: Extending Enterprise Architectures with User Journey Maps. The report provides additional insights in how the validation was conducted and presents the results of the validation in detail.

Validating User Journey Extension for Archimate

In this report, the validation of User Journey Extension for Archimate (UJEA) will be discussed. With the validation, we want to find out the perceptions of stakeholders on the use of the artefact, its collaboration value, and to identify potential improvements. To do this, we will test the artefact in real world conditions. Various UX designers and Architects will play a role in this validation, both applying the artefact to a real case in a banking context, derived from a bank. The bank aims for a 9+ customer experience, and multiple stakeholders are involved to achieve the goal. In practice, it comes down to a collaboration between UX designers, business analysts (BA's) and architects. The collaboration between these parties is valuable; while UX designers and BA's are experts in shaping user journeys, architects help UX designers from a technical perspective. When shaping a user journey or process, architects can see whether the journey is technically optimal and feasible.

For the validation, we conduct a technical action research project. In the technical action research, we will organize an interactive session in which experts apply the artefact to a real case, whereafter we perform a post-it session and a focus group in which stakeholders discuss various aspects of the artefact. During the hands-on session and focus group, we make notes for observational analysis (exploratory, descriptive and explanatory). Additionally, the subjects are asked to write down their opinions on post-its. After the post-it session, group discussions will be held. By gathering notes (observation), subject opinions on post-its, and subject opinions through discussion, we use data source *triangulation* for measuring data for finding patterns that are consistent across different measurements.

1. Research design

In this section, we will discuss the research design of the technical action research. We start by identifying the goal, research questions and variables. Next, we define the scope of the validation, stating which components of the artefact will be validated. What follows, is that we will describe the Contextbank case, the unit of analysis and the subjects for the focus group. Next, we discuss the instruments used for the action research. At last, we finish the research design with the data collection procedure.

1.1. Research Goal

We start our research design by stating the goal of the action research, for which we use the goal template of Wohlin [1]: **Analyse** the use of User Journey Extension for Archimate **for the purpose of** evaluation **with respect to** stakeholder perceptions and intentions **from the point of view** of UX designers and architects **in the context of** improving (technically feasible user journeys. We shorten our goal into Evaluate User Journey Extension for Archimate, and decompose the goal into validation research questions (Questions) and variables (Metrics). The result is shown in Figure 1. The validation research questions and variables will be explained in the next section.

Figure 1: GQM model of the evaluation of UJEA

1.2. Validation research questions & Variables

In this subsection, we state the research questions and variables used to answer the research questions. For shaping our validation research questions and variables, we make use of the Method evaluation model from Moody [2] shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Method evaluation model [2]

The framework provides us with a set of variables (Ease of Use, Usefulness and Intention to use) that have been widely adopted in IT research for evaluation purposes. The first three validation research questions are based on the method evaluation model. In the next paragraphs we discuss the validation research questions (VRQs), variables and how we intend to measure the variables.

VRQ1 What is the perceived usefulness of UJEA?

The first validation research question is focused on measuring the **Perceived Usefulness** (V1): the degree to which stakeholders consider the artefact effective in achieving the intended objectives [2]. With this question we want to see how helpful the artefact would be in practice for stakeholders.

VRQ2 What is the perceived ease of use of UJEA?

The second validation research question is focused on measuring the **Perceived Ease of Use** (V2): the degree to which stakeholders consider using the artefact would be free of effort [2]. With this research question we want to see how difficult or easy stakeholders perceive the use of UJEA.

VRQ3 What is the perceived intention to use of UJEA?

Here we measure the last variable derived from Moody; the **Intention to Use** (V3): the degree that stakeholders intend to actually use the artefact [2]. Here we want to see whether stakeholders would actually use the artefact, or identify situations in which they think the artefact would come of use.

VRQ4 What is the perceived collaboration value of UJEA?

The previous VRQs were focused on the use of UJEA. This VRQ however is focused on whether the artefact actually achieves its main objective: improving the collaboration between UX designers and architects. For this, we create our own variable, the **Perceived Collaboration Value**, which we define as: the degree to which stakeholders perceive the artefact as valuable regarding collaboration with other stakeholders.

VRQ5 To what extent are subjects familiar to user journey concepts?

This VRQ is focused on measuring stakeholder perceptions on the user journey concepts included in UJEA. For this, we measure the **Perceived familiarity of concepts**, which we define as: the degree to which user journey concepts are familiar to the subjects. Measuring this variable shows us whether stakeholders are aware or used to the user journey concepts, which could be of high impact on the other factors. In case some concepts are totally unknown, we could suggest further research on specific concepts or even drop concepts if there is sufficient evidence to do so. We could also have gone for measuring the quality of concepts. However, quality is a large variable that consists of multiple subfactors. Instead, we focus on a more specific variable. To ensure participants still understand the concepts (since they have to apply the artefact), each participant will be provided with a set of descriptions that explains each concept in detail.

VRQ6 What is the perceived completeness of UJEA?

This VRQ is focused on measuring whether the artefact is complete or not. It could be that subjects believe in the potentials of the artefact, but they somehow miss some specific elements. Alternatively, they could have the feeling that the artefact is incomplete, but are not completely sure what is missing. For this matter, we measure the **Perceived completeness**: the degree to which subjects feel the artefact is complete or contains redundant elements.

1.3. Validation scope

The created artefact consists of five components: Mapping of concepts, the New Archimate Framework, the UJEA meta model, a graphical notation and a cross-layer meta model. To make our validation feasible for the time and resources available for the action research, we define a validation scope. For the action research, we focus on validating the user journey concepts of i) the UJEA meta model, ii) the graphical notation and iii) the UJEA cross layer meta model. Though the UJEA meta model will only be partly validated; we merely focus on the user journey concepts as we do not bother the UX designers with a meta model (as they are not familiar to meta models). The validation scope is shown in Figure 3. These artefact parts in specific are chosen because they can be tested in an environment where subjects apply the artefact to a case. These parts play a direct role in the applicability/use of the artefact, while the mapping of concepts and the Archimate framework are merely focused on the structure of the artefact.

Figure 3: Validation scope on the artefact

The validation scope corresponds to the chosen variables in subsection 1.2. When applying the artefact, subjects will get an opinion whether they perceive it as *useful*, *easy to use* and whether they *intent to use* it. Additionally, subjects will recognise or not recognise certain concepts when applying the user journey concepts; allowing us to measure their *perceived familiarity of concepts*. The *perceived collaboration value* does not validate a specific component of the artefact, but measures whether the artefact achieved its objective: improve the collaboration between UX designers and architects. At last, after applying the artefact we expect subjects to have a perception about the *completeness* of the artefact. They might have the feeling to miss some things among the user journey concepts (UJEA meta model, graphical notation), miss a graphical aspect, or miss relations in the cross-layer meta model.

1.4. The Contextbank case and unit of analysis

The action research will be performed at a dutch bank in the Netherlands. Due to privacy regulations, the bank will be referred to as Contextbank. Contextbank is a multiservice provider that aims for a 9+ out of 10 user experience. The 9+ user experience entails that every single digital service provided through the website, app or chatbot should be experienced very well by the users. In attempt to achieve this goal, multiple stakeholders work together. UX designers and business analysts shape and optimize user journeys, whereas solution architects consult UX designers on technical aspects and feasibility of user journeys. A solution architect is an enterprise architect focused on the application architecture. The two stakeholders are quite different from one another in terms of education, work experience and mindset. Where UX designers have a detailed, yet creative focus on creating screen designs and optimizing user journeys, solution architects have a bird-side view and a technical focus on the structure, processes, software and data of the enterprise. As result, collaborating can be a time-consuming process. Yet, collaborating is a vital ingredient for user journeys to be optimal; both from the bank's perspective (technically optimal) and the user's perspective (highly rated user experience). The selected user journey for the action research is the 'becoming a customer online' user journey. The journey describes the flow and experience of the

registration of a new customer, performed by the user through the website or app. The user flow of becoming a customer online is depicted in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Unit of analysis: Becoming a customer

The flow starts with a request for a bank account, followed by a request for a savings account (optional). Next, the user fills in their name, gender and date of birth. Then, the user has to fill in his contact data (e-mail, phone number) and his address. The identification of the user is not complete without a picture of their identity card or passport, so this is uploaded as well. After accepting the terms of agreement, the user pays 1 cent using his existing bank account, as final step to become a customer of the bank.

As the action research is performed at a single case (Contextbank), with only one unit of analysis (becoming a customer online), the design is characterised as a single holistic case study. To provide an overview of the design, an overview is made that shows how the case and unit of analysis are structured. The overview is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Design of the single holistic case study for the Contextbank case

1.5. Subjects

For subjects, we searched for UX designers and architects. As our unit of analysis is the process of becoming a customer online, we searched for UX designers and architects that have at least some knowledge about this process already. Choosing subjects that are familiar to the unit of analysis process mitigates the threat that participants get stuck or keep discussing about the case, rather than keeping the focus on applying the artefact. Also, we tried to find participants that already know each other or have worked together before, which makes the interactive session more attractive for subjects to participate. By asking and mailing around, we found three UX designers involved in customer processes, of which two of them are involved in customer onboarding and are used to work together. Additionally, we found three architects that are all involved in customer processes, and have experience with Archimate. All architects know each other quite well, so the subjects are used to collaborate with the other subjects. As result, we have a total of n=6 participants.

1.6. Instrumentation

For the interactive evaluation session in which we collect the data, we use the following instruments:

- UX designer assignment: A description of the exercise for the UX designers (Appendix A).
- Architect assignment: A description of the exercise for the architects (Appendix A).
- *Powerpoint presentation*: Introduction of the goal of the session, the identified gap, the artefact and the assignments.
- *Completeness questionnaire*: short questionnaire to measure the completeness of the artefact (Appendix A)
- *Graphical notation with concept definitions*: Given to UX designers and architects to explain the elements and graphical notation(Appendix A).

- *User journey example*: To show an example of a user journey created with the artefact, we give the UX designers a user journey example created with the notation. This provides insight to the subjects in positioning and sizing concepts in the right way (Appendix A).
- *Cross-layer meta model*: Given to architects to show the allowed relationships between the user journey layer and other architecture (Appendix A).
- *Informed consent*: A voluntary agreement to participate in research, and that data will only be used for that purpose (and will not be further distributed) (Appendix A).
- *List of rules*: A list of rules will be put on the wall to guide participants in what is allowed and what not during the session (Appendix A).
- *Contextbanks Business Function Model*: Given to architects that they can use to shape the architecture (due to privacy regulations, this document cannot be included in Appendix A).
- *Post-it wall*: Predefined categories in which participants can place their comments
- *Notation concepts printed on paper*: The graphical notation printed on paper that will be used by the subjects to apply the artefact with paper.
- *Post-its*: Small colored papers for writing opinions or comments. Post-its will be put on the post-it wall.
- *Markers & pens paper*: For sketching and writing down opinions.
- *Paper*: Available for sketches.
- *Whiteboard*: Available for sketches.

1.7. Data collection procedure

To validate the artefact, we collect expert perceptions on the identified variables of subsection 1.2. For collecting this data, we organize a two hour interactive evaluation session. For VRQ1-6, we observe subjects (UX designers and architects) as they apply the artefact (i), harvest and analyse the subject's opinions through post-its (ii) and hold a focus group (iii). For VRQ6 (*perceived completeness*), we also use a use questionnaire (Appendix A).

Procedure

The data collection procedure that we follow for the validation is shown in Figure 6. We start the session by giving the participants a warm welcome. This includes setting up a pleasant environment with drinks and cookies to create a relaxed environment. We begin the session with an introduction: a presentation in which we introduce the goal of the interactive session, the gap we aim to fill and the artefact itself. Next, we shortly introduce the case and the assignments. The case and assignments are explained in more detail on the assignments that are given to each subject. As final step before starting, we ask the subjects to fill in the informed consent.

Starting with the session, we plan to have 6 subjects, divided into two teams: One team of UX designers (3) and one team of architects (3). Starting with assignment 1; the UX team creates the user journey of the 'Becoming a customer online' case using the user journey concepts printed on paper. In the meanwhile, the team will work on a different assignment 1; they will have to identify and create the business services, business processes and business functions that are involved in the 'Becoming a customer online' case. When both teams are finished, all subjects will work together on assignment 2. In this assignment, the subjects are asked to the relationships between the user journey and the architecture, using the cross-layer meta model. When the teams are finished linking the architecture to the user journey, we start a post-it session for measuring opinions.

Figure 6: Data collection procedure

In the post-it session, we measure the *perceived usefulness*, *perceived ease of use*, *intention to use*, *familiarity of concepts* and *perceived collaboration value*. These five variables are measured by asking subjects to write down their thoughts on post-its and place them under the matching category on the post-it wall shown on Figure 7. The post-it wall is structured with the 6 variables from subsection 1.2. To see the difference between UX designer- and architect opinions, UX designers place orange post-its on the wall while architects place blue post-its.

<i>Perceived ease of use</i>		<i>Perceived usefulness</i>		<i>Intention to use</i>		<i>Perceived familiarity of concepts</i>		<i>Perceived collaboration value</i>		<i>Improvement suggestions</i>
Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative	

Figure 7: Post-it wall (with fictive post-its as example)

After finishing the post-it session, subjects are asked to fill in a short questionnaire on the *perceived completeness* of the artefact. The questionnaire can be found in Appendix F. After the post-it session, there is a group discussion on all six variables. For each variable, the positive and negative aspects are discussed. The goal of the discussion is to see the “common opinion” among the subjects. We finish the session by thanking the participants and answering questions (if any). As timing is essential for the evaluation session to succeed, we planned the activities in a timetable, shown in Table 1. The timetable merely serves as an indication rather than a strict restriction. The timetable can serve as a red line to ensure all aspects are covered in the session.

Table 1: Schedule for the evaluation session

Who	Activity(s)	Est. time	Schedule
Researcher	Welcome & Introduction (goal, gap, artefact, assignment, case, informed consent)	~20 min	11:00 - 11:20
UX designers	Specify user journey map, observe architecture	~30 min	11:20 - 11:50
Architects	Identify, sketch and visualise relevant business- and application architecture	~30 min	11:20 - 11:50
UX + Architects	Connect user journey to the architecture	~20 min	11:50- 12:10
UX + Architects	Post-it session	~20 min	12:10-12:30
UX + Architects	Group discussion	~25 min	12:30-12:55
Researcher	Wrap up, thank participants	~5 min	12:55-13:00

After the evaluation session, we have gathered data through multiple measurements:

- **Observations:** Observed behaviour of UX designers and Architects as they work on assignment 1 and 2. For the observations, an independent intern at Contextbank was asked to document observations during the session.
- **Post-its:** Opinions that written down on post-its and placed on the post-it wall.
- **Questionnaire:** A short questionnaire on the completeness of the artefact.
- **Audio fragments:** Audio fragments during the assignments and the **focus group**.

By using multiple measurements, we use *triangulation* to search for consistent patterns between multiple datasets.

2. Results

For the evaluation session, we followed the data collection procedure as described in subsection 1.7. We gathered data through: *observations* during assignment 1 and 2, *post-its* on the six defined variables, a *questionnaire* on the completeness of the artefact and *audio fragments* of assignment 1, 2 and the focus group. In this section, we will discuss how the evaluation session went and show the gathered results. The results will be not be analysed yet; this will be done in the discussion (next Chapter). For the results, we start with Observations (2.1.), followed by the Post-it results (2.2.), the questionnaire results (2.3.) and the audio fragments (2.4.). The evaluation session had a sample size of $n=5$, as one UX designer dropped out on the day of the session. This results into two UX designers, three architects.

2.1. Observations

For gathering the observations during assignment 1 and 2, a student assisting the researcher wrote down notes during the evaluation session. For the observations, the assistant focused on how subjects behaved and what subjects said during the assignments. We observed the interactions between participants, whether the artefact was applied correctly, whether the artefact was understood, what participants said out loud, whether they are confused about something etc. For assignment 1, the observational notes were separated for each team. For assignment 2, both teams had to work together, resulting in just one list of observations. The observational notes during the assignments are documented in Appendix B.

Unfortunately, not all observations were written down in the observational notes. With two teams each working on its own assignments which needed some guidance from the researcher, the researcher did not have time to make notes. Thus, further observations on how the assignments went are based what the researcher observed during the assignments (without having the time of writing it down). In the next subsections, we describe how the assignments went and highlight important behavioural observations. Additionally, we describe the result created by the subjects.

Assignment 1

Overall, assignment 1 went well for each team. The collaboration within each team went smoothly and each team started by breaking down the assignment into small parts and creating sketches. The UX team started to identify activities and stages, and the architecture team was sketching business architecture. During this time, the architects had quite some discussion about what the architecture should look like, exchanging each other's experience with the 'Becoming a customer online' case. When the sketches were finished, both teams successfully used the paper concepts to create the 'final' user journey and architecture. It took 50 minutes for both teams to complete assignment one (20 minutes more than expected). Possible causes to the longer duration are due to a longer introduction than planned and discussions on the case during the assignments.

The key observations for assignment 1 are:

- Teams had no issues applying the artefact.
- The UX team forgot to use the channel. When realising this, they created an alternative: putting the channel icon on each 'stage'.
- Moment of truth was repeatedly confused with Opportunity by one of the UX designers.
- Architects were confused to the *optimal* application architecture.

Figure 8 contains pictures of the subjects working on assignment 1.

Figure 8: Assignment 1, team UX design (Left) and team architect (right)

Assignment 2

When the teams started on assignment 2 together to connect the user journey to the architecture, the teams started to discuss each other's work. They were positively surprised that there is a clear link between the created architecture and the user journey, and there was a positive discussion about potentials of the artefact in terms of collaboration.

Key observations for assignment 2:

- Many discussions between UX designers and architects.
- Connecting the user journey to the architecture brought up many discussions about the created user journey/architecture, as well as daily work practice.
- The subjects were interested in each other's way of working, and the discussions can be characterised through positivity and curiosity.
- All three architects wanted to connect their business processes to the activities and stages. According to the meta model, this was not possible; it had to be done through business services.
- One of the UX designers incorrectly explained an architect that the moment of truth icon stands for an improvement.

Figure 9 contains pictures of the subjects working on assignment 2.

Figure 9: Subjects working on assignment 2

Created user journey map and architecture

We can also make observations by analysing the created user journey, the created architecture and the links between both. The result of the user journey linked to the architecture, is shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Created user journey + business architecture of the 'Become a customer online' case

As the content from Figure 10 is difficult to read, a digital replica is created, shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Digital replica of the created user journey + business architecture of the ‘Become a customer online’ case

- Both teams correctly applied the artefact with just a couple of deviations.
- The Goal is included in the user journey map, rather than linked to it.
- Instead of using the channel concept, an app icon was drawn on each stage.
- Instead of linking the architecture to the user journey through business services, the business processes are directly linked.
- Wherever there is an opportunity, there is also a moment of truth.
- All user journey elements were used except the channel.

2.2. Post-its

For the post-its, we follow the categories that were introduced in the data collection procedure (subsection 1.7). In this subsection we discussed the categories on post-it wall that was used for the post-it session. The post-it wall was constructed from the six chosen variables: *perceived ease of use(i)*, *perceived usefulness(ii)*, *intention to use(iii)*, *perceived familiarity of concepts(iv)*, *perceived collaboration value(v)* and *improvement suggestions(vi)*. For the first five variables, we also subdivided the categories into *positive* and *negative*. The post-it session let to a result of 36 post-its in total. Figure 12 shows a photo of the post-its that were placed on the post-it wall. The post-it results have also been digitally processed, which can be found in Appendix B.

Figure 12: Post-it wall with the opinions of subjects

The distribution of the post-its, how they were spread out over the different categories on the post-it wall, is shown in Table 2 below. Overall there were more positive than negative post its. In total, there were 23 positive-, 8 negative-, and 5 improvement post-its.

Table 2: Distribution of post-its over different categories (36)

Variables	#Positive post-its	#Negative post-its	Suggestions for improvement
<i>Perceived ease of use (PEOU)</i>	4	2	
<i>Perceived usefulness (PU)</i>	4	1	
<i>Intention to use (ITU)</i>	4	2	
<i>Perceived familiarity of concepts (PFC)</i>	4	1	
<i>Perceived collaboration value (PCV)</i>	7	2	
<i>Improvement suggestions</i>			5
Total	23	8	5

To show the source of the post-its, whether they represent the opinion of the UX designer or the architect, two tables are created to show the distribution of the UX designer post-its and the distribution of the architect post-its. The distribution of UX designer post-its is shown in Table 3. The distribution of architect post-its is shown in Table 4.

Table 3: Distribution of UX post-its (14)

Category	Perceived ease of use	Perceived usefulness	Intention to use	Perceived familiarity of concepts	Perceived collaboration value	Improvement Suggestion
<i>Positive</i>	2	1	1	2	3	
<i>Negative</i>	1	1	1	0	1	
<i>Improvement</i>						2
Category total	3	2	2	2	3	2
Total	14					

Table 4: Distribution of architect post-its (21)

Category	Perceived ease of use	Perceived usefulness	Intention to use	Perceived familiarity of concepts	Perceived collaboration value	Improvement Suggestion
<i>Positive</i>	2	3	3	2	4	
<i>Negative</i>	1	0	1	1	1	
<i>Improvement</i>						3
Category total	3	3	4	3	5	3
Total	21					

Analysing Table 3 and 4, we see more that there are more architect post-its (21) compared to UX designer post-its (14). This is a logical outcome as the team of UX designers had one subject less than the other team. Additionally, we see that the post-its are quite equally distributed among categories. For UX designers, each category contains 2 to 3 post-its, while for architects the post-its range from 3 to 5.

2.3. Questionnaire

All five subjects filled in the completeness questionnaire (from Appendix F). The results of the completeness likert scales that measure the perceived completeness of the graphical notation and the user journey concepts, are shown in Figure 13. All subjects perceived the graphical notation as quite complete, as all subjects gave it a 4 out of 5. The overall artefact however was perceived as a bit more incomplete with 3 people rating it with a 4 out of 5 and 2 people rating it with a 3 out of 5.

Figure 13: Completeness of the artefact and notation in specific

Additional to the two likert scale questions, the open question of the questionnaire led to the following missing elements:

- Include alternative flows (2x).
- Include risks.
- Include screen designs/ integration with interaction models.
- Allow business processes to connect to the user journey.

2.4. Audio fragments

During the evaluation session, comments on the artefact during assignment 2, the post-it session, the questionnaire and the focus group were recorded. To analyse these comments, we used Nvivo¹. For coding in Nvivo, we follow the same categories as used in the post-it wall, introduced in subsection 1.7. The created nodes are shown in Figure 14. We created nodes for each phase of the evaluation session as well as nodes for each variable. Additionally, the variables perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, intention to use, perceived familiarity of concepts and perceived collaboration value are given two subnodes: Positive and Negative. For the completeness of the artefact, we used the Improvement (completeness) node.

As result, 37 audio fragments with were coded (and 6 evaluation phases). The coded audio fragments can be found in appendix B. How these audio fragments have been coded, is shown in Figure 15. Among these coded fragments, the 37 codes are distributed as follows:

- *Perceived ease of use:* 7 codes (5 positive / 2 negative)
- *Perceived usefulness:* 8 codes (6 positive / 2 negative)
- *Intention to use:* 4 codes (2 positive / 2 negative)
- *Perceived familiarity of concepts:* 2 codes (2 positive / 0 negative)
- *Perceived collaboration value:* 2 codes (2 positive / 0 negative)
- *Improvement(s):* 14 codes

At last, a visual overview of the coded audio fragments is shown in Figure 16. The overview shows the evaluation phases on the top, and tagged comments during assignment 2, the post-it session, the questionnaire and the focus group. Surprisingly, there were no comments on the artefact during assignment 1.

¹ <http://www.qsrinternational.com/nvivo/nvivo-products>

Figure 14: Nvivo nodes; evaluation phases (left) and comment categories (right)

Name	Files	References
Introduction	1	1
Assignment 1	1	1
Assignment 2	1	1
Post-it session	1	1
Completeness questionnaire	1	1
Focus group	1	1
Variables	1	37
Perceived ease of use	1	7
Positive	1	5
Negative	1	2
Perceived usefulness	1	8
Negative	1	2
Positive	1	6
Intention to use	1	4
Negative	1	2
Positive	1	2
Perceived familiarity of concepts	1	2
Negative	0	0
Positive	1	2
Perceived collaboration value	1	2
Negative	0	0
Positive	1	2
Improvement (completeness)	1	14

Figure 15: Coded audio fragments (37) and coded evaluation phases (6)

Figure 16: Coded audio fragments overview

3. Discussion

The previous chapter showed the results for each measurement. In this section, we discuss these results to find consistent patterns across different data measurements in order to answer our six validation research questions (VRQs). For analysing the results, we perform **clustering** on all results discussed in the previous section. Clustering is a technique that can be applied to qualitative data, in which data with similar characteristics is grouped for understanding and conceptualisation [3]. By using clusters, we are able to i) compare results from the observations, ii) post-its, iii) completeness questionnaire and iv) the audio fragments. Additionally, it also allows us to see the amount of positive comments/observations compared to negative ones.

For creating the clusters, we checked for each comment or observation whether that finding was also present in a different data measurement. For example, we could find a positive comment among the post-its that it brings up interesting discussions, which was also observed by the researcher and stated twice by experts. This results in the cluster “Brings up interesting discussions” with a total of 4 findings supporting it. Findings that were only measured in one measurement, are still as a cluster but with just one finding supporting it. In case a comment like “Provides great overview” is found in one of the measurements but not found or observed anywhere else, “Provides great overview” still becomes a cluster, but with only one finding supporting it. Clustering this way allows us to combine large clusters with single findings in one overview.

When clustering the results, we only focus on observations, post-its and audio fragments and completeness questionnaire answers that are focused on the artefact. Comments about the case itself are out of scope for this discussion, as we focus to validate the artefact. Additionally, there are comments that say something about multiple variables. For example, an improvement post-it can be placed on the post-it wall, under familiarity of concepts, while actually indicating that something is missing and thus also belongs to perceived completeness. Another example is that a comment (audio fragment) can be coded as an improvement but also says something about the usefulness. In these cases, the data is put into *both* clusters. Due to this decision, there can be more audio fragments for a specific variable than shown in the coded audio fragments overview of Figure 64.

In the next subsections, we discuss the results for each variable; *perceived usefulness* (3.1.), *perceived ease of use* (3.2.), *intention to use* (3.3.), *perceived familiarity of concepts* (3.4.), *perceived collaboration value* (3.5.) and *Perceived Completeness* (3.6.). The latter is combined with improvements as improvements somewhat indicate that the artefact is as complete as how it should be according to subjects.

3.1. Perceived usefulness

For the perceived usefulness, we created six positive clusters and three negative clusters. The clusters are shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Clusters for perceived usefulness clusters

Perceived Usefulness (PU)						
ID	Description	#Obs.	#Post-its	#Audio fr.	#Quest.	Total
<i>Positive clusters</i>						
PU1	<i>Linking user journeys to architecture is useful</i>	1	1	2		4
PU2	<i>Creates overview & insight</i>	1	2			3
PU3	<i>Allows to perform a gap analysis</i>			2		2
PU4	<i>Brings up informal discussion</i>	1	1			2
PU5	<i>Stimulates re-use of existing architecture</i>			1		1
PU6	<i>Combines company perspective with user's perspective</i>			1		1
<i>Negative clusters</i>						
PU7	<i>Linking only through business services reduces usefulness</i>	1	1	1	1	4
PU8	<i>Screen designs are used instead of user journeys</i>			1		1
PU9	<i>Screen designs are not included</i>			1		1

Positive clusters

The results in terms of perceived usefulness were quite positive, with positive 13 observations/comments on the perceived usefulness. Based on observations, post-its and audio fragments, subjects did perceive linking user journeys to architecture as useful (PU1). Investigating why they perceive these links as useful; the answer could be found within the other positive clusters (PU2-6). The most prominent advantage is the large overview with different insights (PU2) and the opportunity for gap analysis (PU3). The latter has already been explained in the positive cluster discussion for ease of use; it shows experts what links are there, what links are not and results in a to-do list in case there is no supporting architecture while it should be. Another positive aspect is that the artefact brings up discussions (PU4). This aspect is confirmed during assignment 2, as there were many discussions as the subjects linked the models. At last, two positive comments mentioned the artefact stimulated re-use of existing architecture (PU5) and that linking the models combines the perspectives of both the company, and the user (PU6).

Negative clusters

There were quite fewer negative observations/comments that concern the perceived usefulness, with three negative clusters capturing a total of six observations/comments. Though, there is one clear issue that came across all four data measurements, which is that links between journey and architecture must be created through business services (PU7). Architects had a strong preference to directly link the business processes to the user journey activities, which actually goes a little against the Archimates standards. One architect argued *“the artefact has most potential and applicability in connecting the user journey to process modelling, instead of architecture”*. All three architects strongly agreed to this opinion, making this an important improvement suggestion. Another negative aspect in terms of usefulness, are screen designs. Both architects and UX designers agreed that next to user journeys, the screen designs are used a lot as well, and should be considered in terms of the artefact. This results into the two clusters; screen designs are sometimes used instead of user journeys (PU8) and screen designs are not included in the artefact (PU9). Where the first one sees screen designs as an alternative way of showing the same information, the latter contains the idea of including it into the artefact. Screen designs are a visual technique and not just an element, making it difficult to include into the artefact. Though, the idea of creating a similar version of the artefact for screen designs could be a great idea for future work.

3.2. Perceived ease of use

The clusters created from observations, post-its and audio fragments that concern the perceived ease of use are shown in Table 6. As result, there are three positive- and six negative clusters.

Table 6: Clusters for perceived ease of use

Perceived Ease Of Use (EOU)						
ID	Description	#Obs.	#Post-its	#Audio fr.	#Quest.	Total
<i>Positive clusters</i>						
EOU1	<i>Links between user journey & architecture are easy to use</i>	1	1	4		6
EOU2	<i>The user journey & Archimate notation is easy to use</i>	1	1	2		4
EOU3	<i>Adding elements to models is easy</i>		1			1
<i>Negative clusters</i>						
EOU4	<i>Linking user journeys to architecture with business services is inefficient</i>	1	2	1	1	5
EOU5	<i>Moment of truth symbol <!--> confused as Opportunity</i>	2		1		3
EOU6	<i>Pitfall: Many connecting lines</i>		1			1
EOU7	<i>Small learning curve</i>		1			1
EOU8	<i>Channel (not used)</i>	1				1
EOU9	<i>The goal of the user journey was included in the user journey map itself</i>	1				1

Positive clusters

The three different positive clusters capture a total of 11 observations/comments related to the perceived ease of use. The most prominent positive cluster is that creating the links between user journey & architecture are easy to use (EOU1). According to the subjects, not only are the links easy to create, it provides an *“understandable and clear overview of what parts are linked, what parts are not linked and where we should*

take action". Another positive aspect is that the notation of the artefact is perceived as easy to use (EOU2). The architects were known to Archimate and the UX designers were familiar with the user journey notation, stating all concepts were familiar. *"I recognised all concepts, we use the same concepts in my team"*. Both EOU1 and EOU2 were found in three different datasets. At last, one UX designer mentioned on a post-it that it becomes easy to add elements or change an existing user journey (EOU3).

Negative clusters

The negative clusters capture a total of 12 observations and comments, which is quite a similar number compared to the 11 positive ones. The biggest negative cluster concerns how the links between user journey and architecture had to be made (EOU4). This aspect was found in all four different data measurements. Subjects perceived linking the activities to architecture through business services as inefficient. This is quite odd when compared to the most positive cluster, which states that creating these links is easy. This contrast can be explained due to the freedom of participants on how to apply the cross-layer meta model. Participants linked the user journey activities directly to business processes, as they perceive this as a more efficient way of linking the two models. The use of business services to connect the user journey to the architecture is because of the Archimate standards, stating layers should support each other through business services. Another issue was the confusion between of a Moment of truth and an Opportunity (EOU5). Subjects repeatedly perceived the notation of a Moment of Truth as an Opportunity, even incorrectly explaining one of the architects the meaning of a Moment of Truth symbol. The issue here might be caused due to the chosen notation, in that a <!> sign is also a common symbol for an improvement. Other negative aspects were the possibility of having too many lines for connecting elements (EOU6) and that the learning curve is small (EOU7). The latter is expected to be the downside of the simplicity of the user journey notation, but the language can be expanded to solve this issue. Another issue was that the UX designers forgot to use the user journey channel (EOU8). When asked, they were aware of the app as the used channel. Though, the UX designer created a new notation; drawing the app icon on the Stage concept. The last issue in terms of ease of use, is that the user journey goal was included in the journey map itself (EOU9). When asked after the session, the UX designer explained that *"by including the goal into the journey map, the goal does not feel so much separated from the rest"*.

3.3. Intention to use

For Intention to use, there are four positive clusters and three negative clusters. The clusters for intention to use are shown in Table 7.

Table 7: Clusters for intention to use

Perceived Intention To Use (ITU)						
ID	Description	#Obs.	#Post-its	#Audio fr.	#Quest.	Total
<i>Positive clusters</i>						
ITU1	<i>Would use links between journey and architecture</i>		3	1		4
ITU2	<i>Gap analysis</i>			2		2
ITU3	<i>Encourages discussions</i>	1	1			2
ITU4	<i>Initial assessment before creating screen designs</i>			1		1
<i>Negative clusters</i>						
ITU5	<i>Not all UX designers create user journeys</i>			1		1
ITU6	<i>Must be used in the whole company to work</i>		1			1
ITU7	<i>Depends on availability of required data</i>		1			1

Positive clusters

There were nine positive comments/observations that are related to whether subjects would actually use the artefact in their practice. Comments and observations show that the main reasons of using the artefact are the links between journey and architecture (ITU1), the discussions that the artefact triggers (ITU2) and the gap analysis possibilities (ITU3). These clusters were also two in the positive usefulness clusters (PU1, PU3 and PU4). There is a chance that the other positive usefulness clusters such as overview (PU2) also play a role in the intention to use the artefact, but there is no clear evidence they do. At last, the possibility of doing an assessment before creating screen designs is also found to be one of the reasons to use the artefact.

Negative clusters

In contrast to the positive comments/observations, there were only three negative comments. Each negative cluster is based on a single comment. Though, these remarks are still valuable. One UX designer mentioned that not all UX designers create user journeys. “*In my work, I am more focused on screen designs and interaction models rather than user journeys*”. This comment is related to clusters PU8 and PU9, that entail creating or expanding the artefact with screen designs. The other two aspects that would have a negative influence on the intention to use are organisational aspects: the artefact must be used/standardised throughout the whole company (ITU6) and required data must be available to all participants (ITU7). According to subjects, user journeys are not completely standardised throughout the company and that data availability issues are not rare. The data availability issues are related to regulations of rights and authorisations.

3.4. Perceived collaboration value

For the perceived collaboration value, there are five positive clusters and two negative clusters. The clusters are shown in Table 8.

Table 8: Clusters for perceived collaboration value

Perceived Collaboration Value (PCV)						
ID	Description	#Obs.	#Post-its	#Audio fr.	#Quest.	Total
<i>Positive clusters</i>						
PCV1	<i>Stimulates and improves collaboration with UX</i>	1	3	2		6
PCV2	<i>Ensures common understanding</i>	1	1			2
PCV3	<i>Visual connections between each other's work</i>	1	1			2
PCV4	<i>Creates balance between UX & Architect</i>	1	1			2
PCV5	<i>Enables feasibility analysis on UX idea's</i>		1			1
<i>Negative clusters</i>						
PCV6	<i>Incomplete cross-layer meta model</i>	1	1	1	1	3
PCV7	<i>Frequent use of the artefact is a prerequisite</i>		1			1

Positive clusters

In total, there were 13 positive observations and comments regarding the collaboration value. The first cluster (PCV1) provides clear evidence that subjects believe in the collaboration value of the artefact, which will play a large role in answering VRQ4. One UX designer mentioned “*I think it would be a great idea to start using this to communicate with each other*”. The architects were positive as well. One stated “*I definitely see added value in terms of collaboration*”. Other positive clusters probably explain this positive outcome, stating that the artefact improves common understanding (PCV2), visually connects work from UX designers with work of the architects (PCV3), creates a balance between UX designers and architects (PCV4) and allows architects to perform a feasibility analysis on the work of UX designers (PCV5).

Negative clusters

Compared to the 13 positive observations and comments, there were only 4 negative ones. Though, one negative aspect is quite evident: the cross-layer meta model is incomplete (PCV6). This aspect has already come across in the discussion of the perceived ease of use (EOU4) and perceived usefulness (PU7): the architects really want to connect user journey activities to business processes without first creating business services between them. “*Linking these through business services would only take extra time during the collaboration*”. Next to the issue with the cross-layer meta model, one organisational aspect was mentioned; there must be frequent use of the artefact in order to make it work (PCV7). This comment was also mentioned in the discussion of the intention to use (ITU6).

3.5. Perceived familiarity of concepts

For perceived familiarity of concepts, there are three positive- and two negative clusters. The clusters for perceived familiarity of concepts are shown in Table 9.

Table 9: Clusters for perceived familiarity of concepts

Perceived Familiarity of concepts (PFC)						
ID	Description	#Obs.	#Post-its	#Audio fr.	#Quest.	Total
<i>Positive clusters</i>						
PFC1	<i>User journey concepts are familiar / standard</i>	1	2	2		5
PFC2	<i>Envisions UX practice & intentions</i>	1	1			2
PFC3	<i>Architectural structure is familiar</i>	1	1			2
<i>Negative clusters</i>						
PFC4	<i>Missing exceptions</i>		1		1	2
PFC5	<i>Missing risks</i>		1		1	2

Positive clusters

In total, there were nine different positive comments/observations. The most evident positive aspect in terms of familiarity, is that the user journey concepts were familiar to both UX designers and architects (PFC1). The concepts are even recognised as the standards within the organisation. This cluster is supported through multiple data measurements and plays a big role in answering VRQ5. The architectural structure and elements were also familiar to the architects (PFC3). One of the post-its mentioned that the artefact envisions practice and intentions of UX designers. What the subject means, is that recognising the concepts from their collaborations in the past with UX designers.

Negative clusters

In contrary to the positive comments/observations, there were four negative ones. Investigating the negative clusters, we did not observe or hear any comment that a concept was completely new or not understood. Though, subjects did miss exceptions (PFC4) and risks (PFC5) and placed this comment under the familiarity of concepts category on the post-it wall. Apparently these concepts are familiar and expected to be included into the artefact. Although these post-its were placed under familiarity of concepts on the post-it wall, these clusters seem more fit to the perceived completeness.

3.6. Perceived completeness & Improvement suggestions

For the Perceived completeness, we combined the completeness questionnaire answers with the comments and observations on improvements. This decision is based on the logic that an improvement suggestion implicates the perception that the artefact is not complete yet, as the suggestion is still ‘missing’. The findings of the completeness questionnaire are shown in Table 10, along with the improvement suggestion clusters.

Completeness of the artefact (in general) & graphical notation

Starting with the perceived completeness of the graphical notation, the subjects perceived the notation as quite complete, all rating it with a 4 out of 5. The completeness of the artefact as a whole is perceived a bit less, with a avg. rating of 3,6 out of 5. The cause of this lower rate can probably be found in the improvement suggestions. One factor that obviously plays a large role is the incompleteness of the cross-layer meta model. According to subjects, there should be a link possible between (business) processes and architecture. This clustered comment has come across multiple times already in the discussion (perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness and the perceived collaboration value). Another factor that could be of impact are the screen designs; there were multiple comments stating that screen designs should be included in the artefact as they are sometimes used instead of user journeys.

Table 10: Perceived completeness & Improvement

Perceived Completeness (PC) & Improvements						
Questionnaire items (5pt Likert)		Rated by subjects (avg.)				
<i>Perceived completeness of graphical notation</i>		4				
<i>Perceived completeness of artefact as a whole</i>		3,6				
ID	Description	#Obs.	#Post-its	#Audio fr.	#quest.	Total
PC/IMP1	<i>Allow processes to be connected to the journey (activities)</i>	1	2	4	1	8
PC/IMP2	<i>Include screen designs (include or create new artefact)</i>			4	1	5
PC/IMP3	<i>Include alternative flows/exceptions</i>		1	2	2	5
PC/IMP4	<i>Include Risks</i>		1	1	1	3

PC/IMP5	<i>Change notation for Moment of Truth</i>	2		1		3
PC/IMP6	<i>Include requirements</i>			1		1
PC/IMP7	<i>Include required data objects</i>			1		1
PC/IMP8	<i>Change channel notation</i>	1				1
PC/IMP9	<i>Include journey goal into the user journey map</i>	1				1
PC/IMP10	<i>Integrate the language with created personas of the company</i>		1			1

Adjust cross-layer meta model & integrate with screen designs

As for clusters regarding the completeness and improvements, the two clusters just mentioned are the most prominent improvement suggestions found in the study: allowing processes to be connected to user journey activities (PC/IMP1) and including screen designs into the artefact (PC/IMP2). Especially the first one has sufficient support to change the cross-layer meta model, with a total of 8 observations/comments. The subjects did not even connect the models through business services, but drew the links as they wanted (this freedom was given to the subjects, so they still followed the assignment). The screen designs are a different issue. Screen designs seem to be often used instead of user journeys, though both are still quite different. Where screen designs show visual designs with detail already implemented, user journeys are still on a conceptual level. Creating user journeys and assessing them can prevent the situation that screen designs are thrown away after an architect reviews them. The idea of including screen designs into the artefact is a bit unrealistic as well. Screen designs are a visualisation technique on its own, and not on a conceptual or high-level. Still, a solution could be to allow the artefact to connect to created screen designs by introducing new links in the cross-layer meta model.

Including new concepts/elements

A couple of new elements have been requested by the subjects. These suggestions are including alternative flows (PC/IMP3), risks (PC/IMP4), requirements (PC/IMP6) and used data objects (PC/IMP7) into the artefact. From these improvements, the alternative flows and risks should be taken more serious than the other two as they are supported on multiple comments/observations. In terms of feasibility, these suggestions can be implemented quite easily. Though, adding these values comes with a downside; it could reduce the simplicity of the current notation.

Change notation for moment of truth

The notation of a moment of truth was seen as an opportunity (PC/IMP5) by one of the UX designers. This observation gives sufficient reason to change the notation for it.

Alternative notation for Channel

Channel was forgotten by the UX designers even though they were aware of the used channel (PC/IMP8). The UX designer solved this by drawing the same icon on each stage, which could a solution that opens the opportunity to expand the artefact to customer journeys. Drawing the icon on stages and activities opens the opportunity for creating a multi-channel journey.

Journey goal & Persona integration

The last suggestions are including the journey goal into the user journey map (PC/IMP9) and integrating the artefact with the standard personas of the company (PC/IMP10). The first suggestion can easily be adopted by changing the meta model and the illustrative case (that shows an example user journey). For the latter suggestion, the artefact could get a customisation feature when implemented into a company.

4. Summary

To validate User Journey Extension for Archimate (the artefact), technical action research was performed. For the technical action research, an evaluation session was organised with five stakeholders: two UX designers and three Architects. The UX designers were asked to apply the artefact to a case in the banking context: ‘Becoming a customer online’. UX designers were asked to create the user journey for the chosen case, while architects created the relevant business architecture at the same time. When both teams were finished, the two teams came together to link the user journey to the architecture. When the user journey was linked to the architecture, there was a post-it session to gather stakeholder opinions and a short questionnaire was filled in. At last, a focus group was held on the results of the post-it session. In the technical action research, we have gathered data using the following different measurements techniques: observations (i), post-its (ii), questionnaire (iii) and audio fragments with comments (iv).

To validate the artefact, several validation research questions (VRQs) were formulated in section 5.3.2. To answer these research questions, we gathered qualitative data on the following variables: *Perceived ease of use* (VRQ1), *Perceived usefulness* (VRQ2), *Intention to use* (VRQ3), *Perceived collaboration value* (VRQ4), *Perceived familiarity of concepts* (VRQ5) and *Perceived completeness* (VRQ6). To answer these VRQ’s, we clustered the results. By searching for patterns across different measurements and analysing clusters with large comments/observations, we were able to differentiate small comments from important comments that allows us to answer the VRQs.

- VRQ1** The subjects were very positive about the usefulness of creating the links between user journey and architecture (visible in observations, post-its and audio fragments). The other positive clusters showed why they found it useful; it creates overview and insights, allows gap analyses and brings up discussions. One negative aspect that reduces the usefulness, is that the cross-layer meta model does not allow linking business processes directly to the user journey activities. By adjusting the cross-layer meta model, this issue could easily be fixed. Another (smaller) improvement suggestion in terms of usefulness, is integrating or including screen designs into the artefact.
- VRQ2** For ease of use, observations and comments showed that subjects perceived the notation and links between user journey and architecture are easy to use, yet requires improvement. Though the largest negative cluster showed a result that is a bit contradicting; subjects perceived linking user journeys to architecture through business services as inefficient. The reason why subjects still perceived the artefact as easy to use, is that subjects were free in whether they would follow the meta model, or diverse from it. Another important cluster was that the notation of moment of truth was seen as an opportunity. Both the cross-layer meta model and the moment of truth notation can easily be adjusted, fixing the major issues for perceived ease of use.
- VRQ3** In terms of whether the subjects would actually use the artefact (intention to use), subjects were very positive. They agreed that they would use the links between user journey and architecture as it brings up discussions with colleagues, gap analysis possibilities and assessment possibilities before screen designs are actually made. There were only minor aspects that would decrease the chance of using it. These aspects are mainly organisational conditions; required data needs to be available, the artefact must be used throughout the company and the UX designer must be active in user journeys.
- VRQ4** Subjects were very clear that there is positive collaboration value/potential of artefact. One subject even said “*I definitely see added value in terms of collaboration*”. The main reasons supporting their opinion, are that the artefact ensures common understanding, shows visual connections between each other’s work, creates balance between UX designers and architects and enables feasibility analyses. Though, just like the usefulness and ease of use, the cross-layer meta model should be improved to give

the artefact its potential to improve collaboration. Additionally, frequent use of the artefact across the company was again mentioned here as a precondition.

VRQ5 For familiarity of concepts, both UX designers and architects seemed very familiar to the user journey concepts. One UX designer even mentioned the concepts are standardised across the UX design teams. Another positive aspect in terms of familiarity, is that the artefact and the discussion brings the experts in contact again with concepts of from other field (for UX designers: architecture concepts and for architects: user journey concepts). Two improvements in terms of familiarity of concepts, are to include exceptions and risks. One subject wanted to see these concepts included into the artefact.

VRQ6 The artefact was perceived as quite complete, though there is still room for improvement. The completeness of the whole artefact was rated with an average of 3,6 out of 5. The measured completeness of the graphical notation in specific was a bit higher, with an average 4 out of 5. Both avg. scores are above 3 but can still be improved. Multiple improvement suggestions have been found in the evaluation session that could improve the completeness of the artefact. VRQ1,2 and 4 already showed that that the cross-layer meta model needs to be adjusted; allowing a link between business processes and user journey activities. This suggestion describes the largest improvement cluster. Another significant improvement is to either integrate screen designs into the artefact, or be able to link the artefact to screen designs. *The UX designer explained that screen designs are often used as a replacement for user journeys, which should be taken into account for the artefact.* Other improvement suggestions were to include exceptions, risks, requirements and required data objects into the artefact.

5. Conclusion

Overall, the expert's perceptions were positive on User Journey Integrated Architecture. Subjects perceived the artefact as useful, found it easy to use, intent to use it in their work, were familiar to the concepts and saw clear added value in terms of collaboration. Though, the artefact is perceived as not complete (yet), as there is still room for improvement (especially in terms of ease of use). Fortunately, the evaluation session led to a set of improvement suggestions. The major improvement suggestion is that the cross-layer meta model should allow business processes to be directly connected to the user journey. Other prominent improvement suggestions concern artefact integration with screen designs and to include alternative flows and risks. Besides artefact improvements, the evaluation also showed several organisational conditions in order for the artefact to work, concerning the availability of information and method standardisation across the company.

6. References

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APPENDIX A: Action research instruments

A.1. Architect assignment

Opdracht SA: Selecteren en visualiseren van Business- & Applicatie architectuur

Case: Online Klant Worden (OKW)

Introductie

Bedankt dat je meedoet aan deze interactieve sessie! Terwijl de UX designers de user journey van het Online Klant Worden gaan visualiseren op het scherm, is het jouw taak om de bijbehorende architectuur te vinden. Deze architectuur moet vervolgens gekoppeld worden aan de user journey. Deze opdracht doe je samen met de andere architecten. De UX'ers werken apart.

De user flow van het Online Klant Worden (wat de architectuur moet ondersteunen) luidt als volgt:

1. Gebruiker kiest "Betaalrekening aanvragen"
2. Gebruiker kiest "Sparrekening aanvragen"
3. Gebruiker vult naam, geslacht en geboortedatum in.
4. Gebruiker vult contactgegevens in.
5. Gebruiker voegt foto van identiteitsbewijs toe.
6. Gebruiker gaat akkoord met algemene voorwaarden.
7. Gebruiker maakt 1 cent over vanuit zijn/haar bestaande bankrekening

Opdrachtbeschrijving

1. Je hebt verschillende architectuur platen gekregen die slaan op het Online Klant Worden. **Selecteer** en **schets** de relevante business- en applicatie architectuur. Het gaat hier alleen om de **business services, business processes, business functions, application services** en **application components** die het Online Klant Worden proces direct ondersteunen; i.e. wat de klant op de app ziet tijdens dit proces. Verdere offline verwerking van ingevoerde gegevens valt voor deze opdracht buiten scope.
2. Eenmaal vastgesteld en geschetst kunnen jullie de architectuur m.b.v. Archimate te **modelleren** op het interactieve scherm. Dit doe je onder de user journey dat gemaakt is door het andere team. Omdat er maar één scherm is kan dit pas als het andere team klaar is. Zorg dus dat je het ontwerp met een schets klaar hebt liggen.
3. De **koppeling maken** tussen architectuur en user journey. Hiervoor is een meta model uitgedeeld die uitlegt hoe de koppeling gemaakt kan worden.

Aan de slag!

Bestudeer de architectuur platen, gebruik papier om eerst te schetsen en maak er wat moois van. Wanneer de andere groep klaar is met het interactieve scherm kunnen jullie de schets modelleren op het scherm. Mochten er vragen zijn kan je die altijd stellen.

A.2. UX designer assignment

Opdracht UX: Het visualiseren van een user journey

Case: online klant worden (OKW)

Introductie

Bedankt dat je meedoet aan deze interactieve sessie! In deze sessie is het aan jou de taak om een user journey te maken. Deze opdracht doe je samen met andere UX'ers. Intussen zullen de architecten bezig zijn met de bijbehorende architectuur van de journey. De architecten werken echter apart.

Opdrachtbeschrijving

Het is aan jou de taak om de user journey te visualiseren van het Online Klant Worden. Er is een blad gegeven met user journey concepten en de betekenissen. Probeer user journey concepten te identificeren (stap 1) uit het onderstaande scenario, om ze vervolgens op het interactieve scherm te visualiseren (stap 2). Hierbij mogen schetsen op papier gemaakt worden als hulpmiddel.

Persona: Bob

Bob is een 29 jarige sportieve jongen die werkt als consultant bij Deloitte. Hij speelt hoog niveau hockey en houdt ervan als dingen snel geregeld worden. *“Tijd is geld, niet alleen op werk, maar ook daarbuiten”*, denkt Bob. Dit geldt voor Bob ook met dingen online regelen: Bob wil altijd met zo min mogelijk clicks zijn doel bereiken, en irriteert zich al snel wanneer dit niet lukt.

Scenario

Bob wil graag klant worden bij de Rabobank. Allereerst moet Bob zijn productkeuze maken (~10sec). Hij begint met het aanvragen van een betaalrekening. De app vraagt vervolgens ook of hij een spaarrekening wilt. Bob ziet het wel zitten om wat geld te sparen voor de verbouwing, en vraagt dus ook een spaarrekening aan. Eenmaal de productkeuze te hebben afgerond, begint het identificeren (~3min). Allereerst vult Bob zijn naam, geslacht en geboortedatum in. Vervolgens vult Bob ook zijn contactgegevens in. Bob wordt vervolgens gevraagd om een foto toe te voegen van zijn identiteitsbewijs. Eenmaal de foto in het juiste formaat toegevoegd te hebben, begint het afronden (~45sec): Bob gaat akkoord met de algemene voorwaarden, en maakt vervolgens 1 cent over vanuit zijn huidige (oude) bankrekening. Tot nu ging het proces vlekkeloos, maar er gaat nu iets fout; in het keuzemenu van beschikbare banken blijkt Bob's huidige bank, Triodos Bank, er niet tussen te staan. Bob wordt verzocht om het proces opnieuw te doorlopen maar nu via de website, wat grote frustratie opwerkt bij Bob. *“Nu heb ik alles voor niets doorlopen, waar slaat dit op”* denkt Bob. *“Als er een alternatieve optie bestond voor deze laatste stap, was ik nu gewoon klaar geweest”*.

Aan de slag!

Nu het scenario bekend is kun je direct beginnen: identificeer de journey elementen in het scenario en visualiseer het. Niet elk element moet er verplicht in zitten en er is geen perfecte oplossing. Kijk naar wat handig zou zijn voor jezelf wanneer je deze case zou moeten uitwerken. Mochten er vragen zijn kan je die altijd stellen.

A.3. Completeness questionnaire

Compleetheid van het artefact

1. Hoe compleet vind je het artefact in het algemeen?

Erg incompleet

Erg compleet

A horizontal scale consisting of five empty square boxes arranged in a row, used for rating the completeness of the artifact.

2. Hoe compleet vind je de user journey notatie?

Erg incompleet

Erg compleet

A horizontal scale consisting of five empty square boxes arranged in a row, used for rating the completeness of the user journey notation.

3. Indien je wat mist, geef hieronder aan wat je miste (mag alles zijn):

A.4. Graphical notation with concept definitions

Grafische Notatie & betekenissen

<p>User journey map</p>	De totale experience (emoties en gevoelens) van een gebruiker wanneer hij/zij gebruik maakt van een dienst of product via een systeem.
<p>Goal</p>	Het doel van de journey, wat de gebruiker probeert te bereiken.
<p>Experience</p>	De emotie van een gebruiker tijdens een gebruikersactie.
<p>Activity</p>	Een gebruikersactie.
<p>Channel</p>	Het communicatiemedium die de interactie tussen klant en bedrijf mogelijk maakt.
<p>Stage</p>	Een fase in een user journey, gebruikt als container van een groep gebruikersacties die bij elkaar horen.
<p>Persona <Name> Properties: <properties> Goals: <goals></p>	Representatie van een gebruikerstype, bevat een naam, eigenschappen en doelen van het gebruikerstype.
<p>Moment of truth</p>	Een punt in de journey dat de gebruiker een belangrijk of moeilijk besluit neemt, die grote gevolgen heeft op de rest van de journey.
<p>Opportunity</p>	Suggestie voor een verbetering (een idee dat tot user stories uitgewerkt zou kunnen worden)
<p>Timeline</p>	De tijdsduur van een stage of de hele user journey.
<p>Abstraction level</p>	Niveau / detail van de journey (hoe de journey gemaakt is en gelezen zou moeten worden). Kan 2 waardes bevatten: Hoog niveau of Laag niveau.
<p>Thought</p>	De gedachte van de gebruiker tijdens gebruikersacties. De gedachtes dienen als extra uitleg/context op specifieke momenten.

A.5. User journey example

User journey voorbeeld

Cross-layer meta model

A.6. Cross-layer meta model

*Laat de mogelijke koppelingen zien tussen user journey en architectuur

A.7. Informed consent

Informed consent (20/06/2019)

Taking part in the study

- The research information dated 20/06/2019 has been clarified to me. I have been able to ask questions about the study and my questions have been answered to my satisfaction.
- I consent voluntarily to be a participant in this study and that I can withdraw from the study at any time.
- I allow the researcher to make a recording during the study.
- I allow the researcher to take notes while I participate in the study.

Use of the information in the study

- I understand that information I provide will only be used for the master thesis of Lars van den Bos, more specifically in the chapter that deals with the evaluation of his created artefact (User Journey Integrated Archimate).
- I understand that personal information collected about me that can identify me, such as my name or function, will not be shared beyond the study team.
- I agree that my information can be anonymously quoted in research output.

Commitment of the subject

In addition to the agreements above, we ask for your signature as proof of your participation.

Signature of the subject: _____

Commitment of the researcher

I hereby guarantee that non-disclose information and/or data will be kept confidential and that it is only used for academic purposes.

Signature of the researcher: _____

A.8. List of rules

Spelregels

1. Vragen mogen altijd gesteld worden.
2. Overleg met het andere team mag alleen in opdracht 2.
3. UX'ers mogen geen laptop gebruiken. Architecten wel (voor het opzoeken van architectuur).
4. Eerst mag het UX team op het scherm, daarna de architecten.
5. Schetsen mag altijd!

APPENDIX B: Results

B.1. Observations

The following observational notes were taken in Dutch during the evaluation assignments 1 and 2.

Opdracht 1

Opmerkingen & observaties van UX'ers:

- Uxers beginnen te overleggen.
- UX'ers beginnen met een schets het scenario in stukken te breken en te analyseren.
- Ze maken eerst op een wit vel een soort overzichtje met bullet points.
- Er vindt rustig overleg plaats en ze gaan samen door de case. Zijn het niet snel oneens met elkaar.
- Het proces is vrij groot, past nog maar net op het brownpaper.
- De Uxers verwarren moment of truth met opportuniteiten. Leggen nu overall moment of truth neer bij veel proces stappen.
- "ik had niet gezien dat er een ander icoontje op stond, hebben wel in blokken gehad maar alles is mobiel"
- De UX'ers gebruiken het kanaal niet.
- Soms discussie over welke emoticon er moet staan.

Opmerkingen & observaties van architecten:

- Vraag: Zowel business als applicatie architectuur?
- De bestaande case is niks aan veranderd, makkelijk toch?*beginnen met schetsen op het whiteboard*
- Overleggen gemoedelijk.
- Ik zie nu dat hele modelletje weer voor me wat je ooit had uitgetekend (tegen andere architect).
- Zijn echt serieus bezig, uitschrijven van het proces op het whiteboard gaat redelijk vlot en met goed overleg. Kennen het proces goed vanuit hun ervaring.
- Architect zegt ik kan de plaat erbij halen. Volgensmij gaat hij nu een plaat opzoeken van de case die hij eerder heeft gebruikt ooit.
- Ze praten veel uit ervaring over de case.
- Er is een Architect die wat meer de leiding pakt met het schetsen van het proces.
- Maken ook veel gebruik van het business function model.
- Architecten gaan best wel diep op de case op basis van hun eerdere ervaringen. Putten dus ook veel uit eigen ervaring wat betreft de case en niet alleen de gegeven case.
- Een van de architecten vraagt aan de ander: gaan we uit van het proces zoals nu ingeregeld of vanuit als we architect zijn wat we graag willen.
- De flow die we nu uitgetekend hebben is eigenlijk informatieverzameling.
- Andere architect zegt: dan zit er eigenlijk niks in deze architect plaat. Want het is alleen input van de klant. Bulk met data. Er zit geen backend systeem onder. Eigenlijk is nu online klant worden gewoon een groot aanvraagformulier.
- Architecten voornamelijk bezig op het schetsbord, nog niet de modelleertaal papiertjes erbij gepakt.
- De papiertjes van de architecten zijn vrij klein en beetje te weinig.

Opdracht 2

- Architect: "lachen die smileys erbij, dat is echt spot on" deze had wel rood kunnen zijn haha.
- Architect: Gaan we die nu koppelen aan deze rij of ook al aan de nieuwe ideeën?
- Architect: is in ieder geval handig dat je de stappen uit de customer journey hebt en hier hebben wij die van het proces.
- Aandere architect: koppeling die we hier hebben gemaakt zie je hier ook weer terug.
- UX'er: klant ervaart wat maar vanuit de bank ook een aantal stappen nodig om dat onboard proces te begrijpen, dit is dus meer de blik vanuit de bank (architecten plaat) en dit vanuit de klant (UX plaat)
- Architect: die proces laag moet je mappen op de klantenplaat
- UXer vraagt aan architect: jullie begonnen met de proces laag?

- o (er vindt discussie plaats tussen architecten en uxer, dat is wel interessant om te zien. Doordat beide processen naast elkaar liggen gaan ze met elkaar in proces en begrijpen ze misschien ook beter hoe ze werken).
- Architect: voor de order hebben we weer gegevens nodig van de klant identifier. (ze leggen echt dingen uit aan de UXer)
- Architect: dit is wel grappig eigenlijk want dan heb je eigenlijk de proceslaag opgeslagen.
- UXer: daarmee heb je eigenlijk al een nieuwe architectuur bepaald voordat wij de journey helder hebben.
- Er vindt veel discussie plaats tussen de architecten en Uxers.
- Architect: dit (architecten plaat) sluit aan bij wat daar staat (UXer plaat)
- Architect: verwarrende is dat je nu business services wilt koppelen terwijl wij liever de business processen willen koppelen.
- Architect: je moet eigenlijk zeggen dat processen business services leveren en dan die business services koppelen met de UX laag.
- Architect: spreken over orgechstreren van business services, dit is een klein procesje, wat doet die case? Legt vast in relatie management, kleine procesje levert een business service en die orchestreren we achter elkaar. .
- UXer: (12:31): challenge vraag, straat en waar ik woon kan handmatig, maar postcode kan ook automatisch straat enzo invullen. Betekend dat als ik dat zou doen in het scherm dat dat ook hier (architecten plaat) een andere service aanroept? - Architect: ja je wilt het niet steeds opnieuw doen.
- Architect: wil je ze met letters koppelen of met een lijn?
- Gelach tussen architecten en Uxers, positieve samenwerking! Eentje grapt: durf niet over jullie plaat heen te tekenen!
- Er worden nu lijnen getrokken. Één van de architecten neemt hierin het voortouw, vraagt wel aan de Uxers wat ze willen maar over het algemeen tekend ie gewoon zelf wat ie denkt. Uxers kijken aandachtig toe.
- Architect: wat is dit? (op UX plaat), NFC zit dat er ook al in?
- UXer: nee die uitroeptekens zijn verbeterpunten, kritische notes waar het kan worden verbeterd.
- Architect: ‘oh want ik zag het als moment of truth’
- Architect: misschien vanuit coaching overwegingen wel interessant om te praten met iemand van ares, kan dat mag dat?

B.2 Post-it results

Perceived ease of use		Perceived usefulness		Intention to use		Perceived familiarity of concepts		Perceived collaboration value		Improvement suggestions
Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative	
Meta model is easy to understand	Be careful for too many connecting lines	The models provide insight	There seems to be a missing layer in the created architecture to be able to connect it	Encourages people to have a discussion with UX'ers or architects	Must be used across the whole company in order to work.	UX standards are used	Missing risks and exceptions	Allows to test the feasibility of a journey	The cross-layer meta model is incomplete	Connecting process models to the journey instead of business services
You can easily change or add an element to the model	Small learning curve	Provides overview		I would use the connections between journeys to architecture	Users must be able to access the required data (this is not always the case)	Good way of expressing the intentions of UX		Results in earlier understanding of each other's solutions	Must be used frequently to work	I miss a set of elements that I can choose from (relational elements)
The notation was easy to understand		Results in informal discussion		Connections between journeys and architecture are useful		Recognisable architectural structure		Interaction with UX		Execute the experiment digitally instead of the screen
Connecting the user journey to the architecture was easy to do		Connections between journey and architecture is useful		Connections provide one large overview		Results in universal journeys		Creates discussions between UX - architect		Use the 4 standard persona's of the company
								Supports discussion		We now have to create business services first to be able to connect the architecture
								Visual connections that are also useful for the business		
								Creates a balance between UX and architect		

Legend	
	UX post-it
	Architect post-it

B.3 Coded audio fragments

Table 11: Nvivo coded audio fragments

ID	Nvivo code	Audio fragment/comment (in Dutch)
1	Usefulness Positive	"Koppeling tussen user journey en architectuur."
2	Usefulness Positive	"Bankperspectief + Klantperspectief."
3	Usefulness Negative	"Schermen zie je niet."
4	Improvement	"Proceslaag wil je liever koppelen."
5	Improvement	"De business services die uit de proceslaag komen zijn eigenlijk de journey activiteiten. Zelf zijn ze wat overbodig."
6	Improvement	"Koppeling met schermen zou ook nuttig zijn."
7	Ease of use Negative	"<!> tekent zie ik als opportunity."
8	Intention to use Negative	"De user journey laag zelf zal ik niet gebruiken als architect."
9	Intention to use Positive	"De koppelingen zou ik wel gebruiken."
10	Intention to use Negative	"Ik ben hier eigenlijk maar 5% van mijn werk mee bezig, ik ben vooral bezig met schermontwerpen."
11	Improvement	"In schermontwerpen komt eigenlijk nog veel meer naar voren."
12	Improvement	"Alternatieve flows."
13	Improvement	"Excepties."
14	Improvement	"Risico's."
15	Improvement	"Maak het meta model levend: dat er makkelijk dingen toegevoegd kunnen worden."
16	Ease of use Positive	"Makkelijk verbindingen leggen."
17	Ease of use Positive	"Makkelijk te zien waar verbindingen niet zijn."
18	Ease of use Positive	"Makkelijk te zien waar we iets moeten doen."
19	Improvement	"Tets van requirements erin verwerken."
20	Improvement	"Ik wil iets erin waarbij je laat zien wat voor gegevens nodig zijn."
21	Usefulness Positive	"Ik vind het nuttig."
22	Ease of use Positive	"Wij gebruiken percies dezelfde onderdelen."
23	Familiarity of concepts Positive	"Ik herken alle elementen."
24	Ease of use Positive	"Het was makkelijk te gebruiken."
25	Ease of use Negative	"Met de hand is nog net wat meer werk dan digitaal."
26	Perceived collaboration value Positive	"Ik vind het goed om hiermee meer samen te werken met UX."
27	Usefulness Positive	"Het stimuleert hergebruik van bestaande architectuur blokjes."
28	Usefulness Positive	"Geeft mogelijkheid om gap analysis te doen."
29	Usefulness Positive	"Mee eens over de gap analysis."
30	Usefulness Negative	"Er wordt niet altijd een user flow/scenario gebruikt. Het kan ook dat we een bestaande flow qua schermen aanpassen/vernieuwen."
31	Improvement	"Schermen zijn belangrijk, het kan zo zijn dat er 3 schermen nodig zijn voor 1 activiteit."
32	Improvement	"Schermen zijn handig, want voor het bouwen hebben de programmeurs wat visueels nodig."
33	Intention to use Positive	"Qua begin stadia voordat de schermen worden uitgewerkt is dit handig."
34	Collaboration value Positive	"Ik zie sowieso toegevoegde waarde in de samenwerking."
35	Familiarity of concepts Positive	"Ik herken de de concepten."
36	Improvement	"Koppeling via business services weglaten, gewoon processen eraan koppelen"
37	Improvement	"Eigenlijk waar dit het meest van toepassing is, is niet de connectie met architectuur, maar meer de connectie met procesmodellering."